

Original Research Article

Statistical Analysis of Factors Perceived by Taxpayers as Challenges to Tax Compliance in Bujumbura

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The study looked at the factors perceived by taxpayers in Bujumbura as challenges to tax compliance by examining the link between tax education, facilitation of payment, and *quid pro quo*. Dealing with descriptive statistics and chi-square analysis, the study revealed that: the Burundian tax administration has made efforts in tax education with only 8.5% declaring that they are not aware of their tax obligations. The non-computerization of tax payment services is a major challenge which implies the challenge of tax incivism that threatens revenue collection performance. The evaluation of tax payment methods differs among taxpayers according to their seniority, and the chi-square test ($\chi^2=38.346, p=0.001$) shows that at the 99% threshold this difference is significant. It also seems clear that the temptation to evade taxes due to high tax rates is a challenge. Indeed, 43.64% of taxpayers state that if they had the means, they would evade their tax obligations because of the high tax rate. The research hypothesis that "Taxpayers in Bujumbura town generally expect a fair return on their contribution, without which tax evasion is the justified behavior" is confirmed. Indeed, the chi2 test ($\chi^2=28.082; p\text{-value}=0.00$) shows that there is a significant difference between taxpayers' trust in the leadership of the tax administration and the seniority of the latter

Keywords: Accountability, Burundi Revenue authority, defying factors, feedback, *qui pro quo*, Taxes, tax compliance, taxpayers.

INTRODUCTION

The study started from the observation that the awareness of Burundian taxpayers on the need to pay taxes had only become so pronounced with the permanent communication campaigns of the "Office Burundais des Recettes (OBR)" and its strategies to make as many taxpayers as possible comply. The study analyses the strategies mobilized by taxpayers in the city of Bujumbura, stimulated by the communication of the tax administration in claiming social accountability from the government.

This is the Systemic Approach which explains that the notion of a system implies that of homeostasis based on the fact that any system tends to maintain itself in

equilibrium (self-regulation). To understand this, it is necessary to distinguish between positive and negative *feedback*. The interactions between the government and taxpayers are analyzed in light of the notion of feedback. A question heard very often during the awareness campaigns on tax compliance by the "Office Burundais des Recettes" (OBR) since its creation and which is at the origin of this article is: "Why do I have to pay taxes?". Since 2009, the year of the creation of the Burundi Revenue Authority (OBR) as a new tax administration, modern and forced to a gradual performance in the optimization of revenues; a new media discourse around taxes has slowly but steadily settled, supplied by regular debates on the

subject. Indeed, with the OBR, public opinion was becoming increasingly sensitive to the constraints of tax compliance efforts while at the same time the same sensitivity was developing in the direction of demand for government accountability, the quid pro quo. The following question posed in the MIT Gouvernance Lab (2018) seems to us to be more appropriate in the analysis of our problem: "Do citizens who pay taxes to the state have expectations and pressure on their governments for more accountability, democratic representation, and quality services?". This paper addresses the same question but focuses the research on the link between communication with taxpayers and government social accountability in the Burundian context around the question: what are the factors that push taxpayers to develop tax evasion behavior? Taxpayers in the city of Bujumbura generally expect a "fair return" from their contribution, without which tax evasion is justified. Our objective is then to detect the factors stimulating tax evasion among taxpayers in Bujumbura.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Two-step flow of communication theory

Katz and Lazarsfeld developed a theory in 1955 known as the 'two-stage theory of communication'. They showed, through their analysis of the 1948 election campaign, that citizens' opinions are little affected by it. The influence of the media operates in a two-stage process: the information disseminated by the media is first received by each individual, but opinion leaders (people who, through their behavior, have a hold on those around them) filter

The Xs are the awareness-raising actions issued during the campaigns (first stage "receiving information", "putting on the agenda").

The fCA, fBA, and fBC are the processes of influencing and constructing opinions about campaigns and accountability (second 'tier': ownership of information). The OBR conducts awareness campaigns (X). They directly reach citizen-taxpayers (B), but also their associations (C). Citizen-taxpayers build their opinion based on these two streams of influence which combine and in which "influencers", opinion leaders (A) intervene at two levels (feedbackBA - feedback CA). In total, the opinion of taxpayers and their reaction to campaigns and accountability will result from the interaction of these levels of influence (fBC) as developed in (Shannon, 1948).

Literature on the concept of accountability

The literature on accountability has been used to understand this concept and its relationship with communication with taxpayers. This will be an

the information and influence the opinion of individuals, who then relay it to the rest of the population during interpersonal conversations.

To handle the challenges to tax compliance by examining the link between tax education, facilitation of payment, that means to analyse also the link between facilitation thanks to technology and the social impact related to tax education. This is how, from the beginning of the 1990s, the foundations were laid "against the radical separation between technology and society" (Flichy, 2008) and for an "interactive technical-social approach", a "complexity of interpenetration" (Bardini, 1993, Millerand, 1998). Several sociological theories of techniques will influence this trend of sociotechnical interactionism in the co-construction of innovation. These are the theories of translation, the sociopolitics of uses, and the theory of innovation.

Theoretical concept of feedback

Indeed, when speaking of retroactive capacity, it is clear that we will approach this concept from the confined angle of the social accountability of the state, which, as the legal and exclusive collector of taxes and duties, becomes accountable to citizens in return for quality services. The study finds that the notion of feedback as developed is intended as an aspect of observation during the research method. The following diagram shows that at a certain point the partners are obliged to remain connected in an endless retroactive interaction. According to Ernste (2014), Westley and Mc Lean's diagram can be adapted to our research to summarise the observed interactions:

exploration of the literature developed on the link between tax and governance, tax and government accountability, and tax and state development. Mick Moore's study summarises the policy implications of a growing debate on the links between tax compliance and the quality of governance in country development. According to the author, tax compliance - or the lack of it - has an impact on the quality of governance through two main channels. The first concerns the degree of dependence of governments on the general taxation of their financial resources. Many governments do not need to put much effort into revenue mobilization because they have large revenues from oil, gas, and mineral exports or foreign aid. This changes the political incentives that political elites elsewhere face and how they seek to gain, use and retain power. The long-term consequences for governance are adverse: elected officials are less responsive and accountable to citizens; and, with revenue sources largely independent of tax revenues, governments may have less incentive to build a political and organizational framework that makes state capacity

robust. States are likely to be both arbitrary and weak. Other things being equal, (the second channel) governments' reliance on taxation affects the quality of governance, the author says. But this relationship is not automatic. "We cannot say, because they are fully dependent on tax revenues, that governments will be capable, accountable, or responsive. They may collect taxes in a coercive manner, thereby undermining the promotion of tax compliance and reinforcing bad governance. Governments in some developing countries still tend to impose tax compliance in a coercive manner. Yet, establishing more consensual tax procedures between the state and taxpayers is an important way to improve governance. Research shows that participatory institutions that have deepening democracy as their primary objective struggle with institution building more than reforms that tap into opportunities opened by major reforms driven by sectoral needs (Oliveros and Mayka, 2022).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To understand the compliance behavior of taxpayers in Bujumbura city and their mind behind the tax, the study seeks to discover the factors perceived by taxpayers as a barrier to fiscal civism. To capt those factors, the study uses a questionnaire that leads the assessment according to the Likert scale.

Source and method of Data collection

To answer the research question, we submitted a questionnaire to taxpayers from Bujumbura City whose themes sought to collect data on factors perceived by taxpayers in the city of Bujumbura as challenges to tax compliance. The instrument included topics such as tax education, ease of tax payment, and quid pro quo and was administered to 750 taxpayers in Bujumbura city out of 768 individuals who were calculated using the relationship $n = z^2 p(1-p) / e^2$ (Giezendanner, 2012) i.e a response rate of 97.66%

Method of data analysis

The analysis and interpretation of the results were done using SPSS(IBM statistics 25) software. Using SPSS, the study deals with descriptive statistics to highlight the

factors perceived as barriers to tax compliance by taxpayers. The study conducted also a chi-square analysis to detect the link between the seniority of taxpayers and confidence in leadership on one hand and the evaluation of different taxes among taxpayers, on another hand

RESULTS

This section presents the data collected from taxpayers in Bujumbura City to capture the factors perceived by Burundian taxpayers as challenges to tax compliance, which is a guarantee of economic development.

Socio-demographic and professional characteristics of respondents

Of these taxpayers, 57.3% are in the trade sector, 12.3% in the agri-food sector, and hotels and restaurants. Generally, all taxpayers are from local companies and only three of them are multinational companies. The public sector is the most represented and the private sector accounts for 4.4% of the taxpayers surveyed, while 0.7% are from mixed (private and public) enterprises. In general, most of the respondents' companies are young. Indeed, 34.4% have been in existence for between 1 and 4 years, 24.9% for less than a year, and 24.4% for between 5 and 9 years. 16.3% have been in business for more than 10 years, of which only 2.4% have been in business for more than 20 years.

Tax Education

Generally, taxpayers are aware of the tax obligations of their companies. However, 8.5% stated that they were not aware of their company's tax obligations. On the other hand, 95% of respondents stated that they had never refused to pay a tax, 3.6% stated that they refused to pay from time to time, and 0.3% that they often refused to pay. On the other hand, 43.64% of taxpayers say that if they could afford it, they would avoid their tax obligations because of the high rate. The lack of information on the payment of tax, its role (visible work), and the visible counterpart of taxes are also more underlined as convincing causes of evasion of tax payment by 25.97% and 19.68% respectively. Lack of trust in tax officials (10.71%) and corrupt practices are also highlighted (6.16%). However, 14.2% said that no reason whatsoever would prevent them from meeting their tax obligations.

Figure 1: Distribution of evidential causes of tax evasion
Source: Researcher's computation

In addition, the leadership of the tax administration to taxpayers is not satisfactory. It is noted that 23.1% of the taxpayers have a low level of confidence in the leadership of the tax administration while 23.7% have a medium level of confidence. However, 53.2% have a high level of confidence. It can be seen that this confidence varies

according to the seniority of the taxpayer. Indeed, the chi-2 test ($\chi^2=28.082$; $p\text{-value}=0.00$) shows that there is a significant difference between taxpayers' confidence in the leadership of the tax administration and the seniority of the latter.

Figure 2: Perception of the role of taxes in the country's development
Source: Research's computation

The taxpayers surveyed are aware of the importance of taxes in the economic development of a country. Most respondents (74.9%) say that the role of taxes in development is important and 24.9% manage to state that it is extremely important. Although the importance of taxation is widely known, most taxpayers feel that the benefits of taxation are limited to certain categories of the population. These are mainly government officials who are seen as the main beneficiaries. Most of the traders interviewed felt that, although they were the main contributors to the tax bill, they were the last to benefit from it.

Assessment of the taxfield

Companies have to fulfill tax obligations via the tax administration. The procedures required to pay taxes are generally appreciated. However, 29.9% of respondents find these procedures difficult and 33.6% say they are average. This view remains the same about payment methods, which are described as difficult by 44.5% and as average by 25.7%. However, the waiting time for tax payments is mainly seen as average by 57.2% of respondents and 39.3% say that the waiting time is short, of which 15.6% say it is very short. The evaluation of the payment of taxes differs among taxpayers according to their seniority, the chi-square test ($\chi^2=38.346$, $p=0.001$) shows that at the 99% threshold this difference is significant.

It was found that taxpayers feel that the tax administration does not encourage a culture of transparency through the development of ICT in the payment of taxes. This finding is confirmed by 69.2% of the taxpayers surveyed. Indeed, only 3.6% of respondents use electronic tax payments. Most taxpayers (69.3%) also

feel that the government is not making an effort to put in place procedures and innovations for dematerialization and facilitation (e.g. digitization of new procedures, new programs, etc.). The same applies to the handling of taxpayers' grievances by tax administration employees, which 56.3% of respondents find less rapid. The seniority of the taxpayers means that they find the handling of their complaints by the tax administration different. Indeed, the chi2 test shows this difference.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Tax compliance is the result of several combined actions detailed in this study through three axes, namely tax education, facilitation of payment through ICT, and government accountability (Tsai, Toral, Read and Lipovsek, 2008). In particular, the study highlighted the major importance of the return of taxes paid in terms of development programs. Thus, it concurs with Mick Moore's study which summarises the policy implications of a growing debate on the links between tax compliance and the quality of governance in the development of countries. Otherwise, respondents do not hesitate to acknowledge the temptation of tax evasion. As the literature review highlighted, taxpaying citizens are aware of the importance of taxes. (74.9%) say that the role of taxes in development is important to the state, but the study reveals their dissatisfaction with the expectations in terms of compensation. Indeed, most of the traders to whom the questionnaire was submitted find that, although they are the main contributors to the tax bill, they are the last to benefit from it. This state is confirmed by the OECD (2018): "Despite recent improvements in economic performance, many economies continue to experience low productivity growth and often stagnating wages, as well as increased levels of inequality."

Although the Burundian tax administration has made efforts in tax education with only 8.5% declaring that they are not aware of their company's tax obligations, the non-computerization of tax payment services is a major issue in tackling the challenge of tax incivism that threatens revenue collection performance. It seems clear that the temptation to evade taxes because of high tax rates is a challenge. Indeed, 43.64% of taxpayers say that if they had the means, they would avoid their tax obligations because of the high rate. If the loss of time in paying taxes by honest taxpayers is added to this discouraging perception, then there is an urgent need to computerize procedures and act on the general tax policy that impacts the decision of tax rates. However, Paquienséguy (2007), Badillo and Pélissier (2015), Coutant (2015), update the socio-technical tensions and interactions in today's informational and digital society, while highlighting the preponderant role of the "user".

This tax policy is normally reviewed annually during the revisions of the annual budget laws, which are sessions of interaction between the government and taxpayers. The Westley and McLean diagram show that at some point the partners are forced to remain connected in an endless retroactive interaction. It is these interactions that open up the possibility of more consensual tax procedures between the state and taxpayers, which is an important avenue for improving governance.

CONCLUSION

The study sought to uncover factors perceived by taxpayers in the city of Bujumbura as challenges to fiscal incivism by investigating a link between tax education, facilitation in payment, and return in terms of government accountability. The research hypothesis was taken up here: "Taxpayers in the city of Bujumbura generally expect a fair return on their contribution, a condition without which fiscal incivism is justified behavior" is confirmed. Indeed, the study concludes that the fight against tax evasion could yield convincing results if the government works on controlling the tax rate, commits to the digitalization of tax procedures, and finally strives to ensure national development as a guarantee of the return of taxes paid for accountability.

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